

ASSESSMENT OF THE VIRUCIDAL EFFECT OF A COMMERCIAL BIOCIDES AGAINST TWO DIFFERENT STRAINS OF NERVOUS NECROSIS VIRUS, BETANODAVIRUS

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Introduction

Viral nervous necrosis (VNN) is the most threatening infectious disease in Mediterranean aquaculture. VNN is caused by the nervous necrosis virus (NNV) a small naked ssRNA⁺ virus, highly resistant in the aquatic environment. Four genotypes of NNV have been so far described: RGNNV, SJNNV, BFNNV, TPNNV among which the RGNNV is the most spread in the Mediterranean Sea. European sea bass (*Dicentrarchus labrax*) is one of the species most affected by VNN, however the emergence of a reassortant strain RGNNV/SJNNV caused high mortality outbreaks also in gilthead sea bream (*Sparus aurata*) larvae (Volpe et al., 2020). So far, no therapy is available for VNN control and vaccination is applied limited to on-growing facilities, therefore the control in hatchery is strongly based on direct prophylaxis aimed to prevent the entering and the spreading of the virus in the farms. In this respect the setup of effective hygiene standard procedures can greatly contribute to the reduction of the VNN impact.

The aim of this study was to assess the *in vitro* virucidal activity of a commercial compound (Virkon® S) towards the two NNV variants most spread in the Mediterranean Sea.

Materials and methods

Two NNV strains isolated during mortality outbreaks (Ciulli et al., 2006; Volpe et al., 2020) previously characterized as RGNNV genotype (It/351/Sb) and reassortant RGNNV/SJNNV (Sa-416-Dec17) were propagated in cell culture SSN-1 and tested for *in vitro* virucidal activity.

Suspension virucidal activity of a peroxy-acid commercial compound (Virkon® S) was assessed first using the European UNI EN 14675 standard “Quantitative suspension test for the evaluation of virucidal activity of chemical disinfectants and antiseptics used in the veterinary area” adapted to test aquatic pathogens (Verner-Jeffrey et al., 2009). Fixed temperature (20°C) and exposure time (5 min) were used, whereas variable biocide concentrations (0.5 vs 1% w/v) and soiling conditions (low soiling LS vs high soiling HS) were tested. Sea water was used as diluent.

In order to establish whether the tested biocide for use on instruments (nets, cages, etc) has a virucidal activity in the fields, a new protocol (net test) closely simulating practical conditions of application was developed. Briefly pre-drying viruses on a carrier (nylon net) were titred after incubation with or without biocide treatment. Contact time, temperature, test organisms, biocide concentrations and soiling conditions were tested as in the previous assay.

Results

A similar virucidal effect was demonstrated for Virkon® S against the tested NNV strains representing the RGNNV genotype and the RGNNV/SJNNV reassortant strain.

Suspension test: a titre reduction (TR) $\geq 4 \log(10)$, considered effective by the EN 14675 standard, was demonstrated for the tested biocide at the concentration of 1% w/v under both low and high soiling conditions consisting in a reduction of 99.99% of the viral TCID₅₀ of It/351/Sb or Sa-416-Dec17 strains. Similarly, a titre reduction (TR) $\geq 4 \log(10)$ was observed for the tested biocide at the concentration of 0.5% w/v towards both strains when tested under low soiling condition. When tested under high soiling condition at the 0.5% w/v concentration, the biocide showed a higher titre reduction towards the strain It/351/Sb, however at this condition no effective TR was reached ($\leq 4 \log 10$).

Net test: a titre reduction (TR) $\geq 4 \log(10)$ was obtained for the tested biocide at the concentration of both 0.5 and 1% w/v only under low soiling condition for It/351/Sb viral strain. A slightly lower TR was observed under high soiling condition (TR 3.3 and 3.5 log (10) at 0.5 and 1% w/v respectively) for It/351/Sb strain. Regarding Sa-416-Dec17 strain TR was similarly influenced by biocide concentrations and soiling conditions, even if all TRs were $\leq 4 \log(10)$. However, Sa-416-Dec17 strain test was partially affected by the net drying process resulting in lower starting viral titres.

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Discussion and Conclusion

The tested biocide was found to be suitable for NNV inactivation being effective under at least some of the conditions tested. However, the presence of the organic matter, the concentration of the product and the application conditions (suspension vs net) can significantly affect the result of the disinfection procedures. For these reasons, it is of paramount importance to set up a specific disinfection protocol considering the “cleaning” level that can be reached before disinfection. Both tested strains representing the RGNNV genotype and the RGNNV/SJNNV reassortant strain were affected similarly by tested conditions, however Sa-416-Dec17 strain showed a higher susceptibility to drying process and a lower susceptibility to biocide treatment compared to It/351/Sb. The results obtained in this study led to stress the application of effective disinfection protocols preceded by surface cleaning and drying step in order to reduce the VNN impact at farms.

References

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